

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

***BULLETIN OF* FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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CHARACTERISTICS OF QUANTITATIVE INDICATORS OF IMMUNOGLOBULINS IN THE BLOOD SERUM OF PREGNANT AND LACTATING WOMEN

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Resume. The aim of this study is to develop a differentiated approach to assessing immune status by comparatively analyzing the quantitative indicators of immunoglobulins in the blood serum of pregnant and lactating women. It was also demonstrated that pathological conditions affect the humoral component of the immune system, and the resulting immune system stress leads to an increase in immunoglobulin synthesis.

Keywords: antigen, autoimmune thyroiditis, reference values, monomers, dimer, pentamer, placenta, complement

ХОМИЛАДОР ВА ЭМИЗИКЛИ АЁЛЛАРНИНГ ҚОН ЗАРДОБИДАГИ ИММУНОГЛОБУЛИНЛАРНИНГ МИҚДОРИЙ КЎРСАТКИЧЛАРИНИНГ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ

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Резюме. Ушбу тадқиқотнинг мақсади ҳомиладор ва эмизикли аёлларнинг қон зардобидаги иммуноглобулинларнинг миқдорий кўрсаткичларини таққослаш орқали иммунитет ҳолатини баҳолашга дифференциал ёндашувни ишлаб чиқишдир. Шунингдек, патологик шароитлар иммунитет тизимининг гуморал компонентиға таъсир қилиши ва натижада иммунитет тизимининг стресси иммуноглобулинлар синтезининг ошишиға олиб келиши кўрсатилган.

Калит сўзлар: антиген, аутоиммун тиреоидит, мос ёзувлар қийматлари, мономерлар, димер, пентамер, плацента, комплемент.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ КОЛИЧЕСТВЕННЫХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ ИММУНОГЛОБУЛИНОВ В СЫВОРОТКЕ КРОВИ БЕРЕМЕННЫХ И КОРМЯЩИХ ЖЕНЩИН

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Резюме. Целью данного исследования является разработка дифференцированного подхода к оценке иммунного статуса путем сравнительного анализа количественных показателей иммуноглобулинов в сыворотке крови беременных и кормящих женщин. Также было показано, что патологические состояния влияют на гуморальный компонент иммунной системы, а возникающий в результате стресс иммунной системы приводит к увеличению синтеза иммуноглобулинов.

Ключевые слова: антиген, аутоиммунный тиреоидит, референсные значения, мономеры, димер, пентамер, плацента, комплемент.

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Relevance of the Problem. Protecting the health of women of reproductive age during pregnancy and the postpartum lactation period is one of the most important tasks of any national healthcare system. In this regard, special attention is being paid to scientific research aimed at predicting, preventing, and early diagnosis of pathological conditions that may arise during these periods.

During normal pregnancy, physiological, hormonal, and immunological adaptations highlight the complexity of understanding how susceptibility to infections and related complications is influenced. Key adaptations at the maternal–fetal interface represent essential processes [4, 6]. Maternal antibodies are a major component of immunity that provide immediate protection to the newborn after birth [1].

Non-cytotoxic maternal antibodies directed against paternal antigens have been identified in most women experiencing normal pregnancies during the first trimester, whereas they were absent in the majority

of women who experienced miscarriage. This suggests that these antibodies may play a crucial role in successful pregnancy outcomes.

It has been established that the maternal immune system contributes to the development of passive immunity in the fetus by providing protective factors against infectious diseases. In addition, maternal immunoglobulins are recognized to have the ability to stimulate fetal growth [2, 5, 7].

According to studies by Nuraliev N.A. and Mustafaeva F.A. [3], a decrease in cellular and humoral immunity, along with multidirectional changes in pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines, was observed in acute and chronic inflammatory diseases of the pelvic organs, indicating the development of secondary immunodeficiency.

Although a number of scientific studies have been conducted on this issue, no differentiated approaches have been developed to assess immune status through a comparative analysis of quantitative indicators of immunoglobulins in the blood serum of healthy pregnant and lactating women living in rural areas. Furthermore, immune-related diseases within the “pregnant–postpartum–lactating woman” system have not been comparatively studied, and diagnostic as well as prognostic criteria adapted to specific geographical living conditions have not been developed. This necessitates further research on this topic.

Discussion of Research Results. It is well known that immunoglobulins are specific proteins (γ -globulins) synthesized by the immune system in response to antigen entry into the body, and they possess several distinctive characteristics. Currently, five classes of immunoglobulins are identified, four of which have significant pathogenetic importance: IgM, IgA, IgG, and IgE.

During the course of this dissertation research, it was considered necessary to study and analyze the quantitative indicators of these immunoglobulins in pregnant and lactating women. Before interpreting the obtained data, a brief characterization of these immunoglobulins was provided.

IgM is a pentameric immunoglobulin and is phylogenetically the earliest to be formed. It has a molecular weight of approximately 900 kDa. Its highest concentration in the blood is observed 4–5 days after antigen entry into the body, after which it gradually decreases, remaining in the body for up to 5 days.

IgG is a monomer with a molecular weight of about 150 kDa and constitutes approximately 75% of total immunoglobulins in the body. It begins to be synthesized 5–6 days after primary antigen stimulation and has the longest persistence in the body—up to 23 days. In the case of a secondary immune response, its synthesis starts from the first day.

IgA exists in both serum and secretory forms. In serum, it is present as a monomer, while in secretory form it exists as a dimer. The serum form accounts for about 15% of all immunoglobulins.

IgE is a monomer with a molecular weight of approximately 190 kDa and has a short half-life of about 2–3 days. It differs from other immunoglobulins by the larger size of its heavy (H) chains and the absence of a hinge region. It is considered a marker of various allergic processes (Table 1).

Table 1

Comparative Characteristics of Serum Immunoglobulins (according to Nuraliev N.A. et al., 2010)

Ig	Molecular Weight (kDa)	Configuration	Placental Transfer	Complement Binding	Normal Level (Serum)
IgM	900	Pentamer	-	+	1,0 g/L
IgG	150	Monomer	+	+	12-20 g/L
IgA	160	Monomer	-	+	2,4 g/L
sIgA	380-385	Dimer	-	-	Variable
IgE	190	Monomer	-	-	0,0003 g/L
IgD	184	Monomer	-	-	0,003 g/L

Further Analysis of Research Results. Given the important role of immunoglobulins in clinical immunology, their levels were studied in pregnant and lactating women. A total of 92 pregnant women were examined, and the quantitative levels of different classes of immunoglobulins in their blood serum were analyzed. After delivery, these studies were repeated in the same women during the lactation period.

The participants were divided into three groups: healthy women ($n = 20$), women with autoimmune thyroiditis ($n = 36$), and women with grade I–II anemia ($n = 36$). For more adequate interpretation, patients with pathological conditions were combined into a general group and compared with the indicators of healthy women.

The obtained results showed (Table 2) that the level of IgA in healthy women was 1.76 ± 0.77 g/L, while in the general group it was 1.70 ± 0.08 g/L. As can be seen, no statistically significant difference was observed between the compared groups ($p > 0.05$).

Table 2

Quantitative Indicators of Major Immunoglobulins in the Blood Serum of Pregnant Women

Indicators	IgA, g/L	IgG, g/L	IgM, g/L	IgE, IU/mL
Reference values	1,0-2,0	12-20	2,4	3
Healthy pregnant women (n=20)	1,76±0,07	20,35±0,18	2,10±0,08	138,82±0,89
General group n=72	1,70±0,08↔	19,85±0,26↔	2,48±0,14*↑	162,65±0,68*↑

Note:— statistically significant difference compared to healthy pregnant women, ↑ — direction of change (increase), ↔ — no statistically significant difference.

Interpretation of Results. However, when these indicators in pregnant women were compared with the reference values of healthy non-pregnant individuals (average 1.0 g/L), a noticeable increase was observed. The elevated serum concentration of IgA in pregnant women compared to reference parameters can be explained by the specific characteristics of the immune system during pregnancy. The similarity between the values in healthy and pathological groups indicates that diseases do not significantly affect IgA quantitative levels.

A similar trend was observed for IgG. The values in healthy pregnant women and in the general group were 20.35 ± 0.18 g/L and 19.85 ± 0.26 g/L, respectively ($p > 0.05$). Although no statistically significant difference was found between the groups, both values were slightly higher than the reference range (12–20 g/L).

In contrast to the previously analyzed immunoglobulins, IgM showed a statistically significant increase in the general group compared to healthy pregnant women: 2.48 ± 0.14 g/L versus 2.10 ± 0.08 g/L ($p < 0.05$). A similar pattern was observed for IgE: 162.65 ± 0.58 IU/mL versus 138.82 ± 0.89 IU/mL ($p < 0.05$).

The difference between the groups showed that IgM levels increased by 1.18 times, while IgE levels increased by 1.17 times in the general group compared to healthy pregnant women ($p < 0.05$).

In our opinion, the increased tendency of IgM and IgE in pregnant women compared to those with autoimmune thyroiditis and various degrees of anemia (general group) can be explained by antigenic stimulation of the organism. Pathological conditions influence the humoral component of the immune system, and the resulting immune stress leads to increased synthesis of immunoglobulins. Analysis of the functions of these immunoglobulins suggests an enhancement of the primary immune response and an increase in allergic background.

Thus, the study of major immunoglobulin levels in the blood serum of both healthy pregnant women and those with various pathological conditions showed that there were no statistically significant differences in IgA and IgG levels between the compared groups ($p > 0.05$). The numerical values were very close, although slightly elevated compared to reference values. This increase is not considered a sign of pathology but rather a physiological imbalance associated with pregnancy.

Although statistically significant differences were observed between the groups for IgM and IgE (increases of 1.18 and 1.17 times, respectively), the values remained relatively close. These changes are also interpreted as physiological adaptations associated with pregnancy rather than pathological deviations.

Conclusions:

1. It was established that the quantitative indicators of immunoglobulins of different classes in the blood serum of both healthy pregnant women and women in the general group were slightly higher than the reference values (12–20 g/L).

2. IgA levels in the general group were lower compared to healthy pregnant women, they remained relatively elevated compared to reference values. This is explained by the specific features of the immune system during pregnancy. The similarity of indicators between healthy and pathological groups suggests that diseases do not significantly affect IgA levels.

3. Observations on IgM and IgE Levels. The quantitative indicators of IgM and IgE in healthy pregnant women showed an increasing trend compared to women with autoimmune thyroiditis and various degrees of anemia (general group). This suggests that antigenic stimulation of the organism, the influence of pathological conditions on the humoral branch of the immune system, and immune system stress lead to increased synthesis of immunoglobulins.

References:

1. Dobrokhotova Yu.E., Bakhareva I.V. Iron-deficiency anemia: prevention and treatment during pregnancy // *Lechebnoe Delo*. – 2016. – No. 3. – P. 4–13.
2. Kalandarova A.N., Zhiemuratova G.K., Kadyrova A.M. Immunological aspects of COVID-19 in women of reproductive age // *South Kazakhstan Medical Academy, Bulletin*. – No. 2(96). – 2022. – P. 144–147.
3. Nuraliev N.A., Mustafaeva F.A. Assessment of immune status and effectiveness of immunocorrection in inflammatory diseases of the pelvic organs in women // *Doctor's Bulletin*. – No. 3.1 (96). – 2020. – P. 140–147.
4. Khalimova F.T., Shukurov F.A., Nurmatov A.A. Assessment and prediction of reproductive health in women of fertile age // *Bulletin of the Academy of Medical Sciences of Tajikistan*. – 2019. – Vol. IX, No. 2. – P. 199–208.
5. Abu-Raya E., Michalski C., Sadarangani M., Lavoie P.M. Maternal immunological adaptation during normal pregnancy // *Frontiers in Immunology*. – 2020. – No. 11. – P. 1–18.
6. Baturin V.A., Boshyan R.O. The immune status of outpatient women of reproductive age with pelvic inflammatory disease // *Medical News of North Caucasus*. – 2018. – No. 13(3). – P. 493–496.
7. Musakhodjayeva D.A., Karimov R.K., Rasulova S.Kh. Immunological indicators of complications of surgical bowel disease in children // *Medical Immunology (Russia)*. – 2023. – No. 25(4). – P. 907–912.

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